

Population densities of brown planthopper (BPH) and its predators, and ragged stunt disease (RSV) incidence in central Thailand, April-June 1981.

Species	Sampling method	No. ^a	Occurrence in sampling areas (%)
BPH <i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	Direct count	204.3	95.2
	Sweep net	6.5	75.7
BPH eggs	Stem dissection	61.4	78.8
Damselflies	Sweep net	23.2	100.0
<i>Lycosa pseudoannulata</i>	Direct count	7.8	97.6
	Sweep net	2.1	37.8
<i>Tetragnatha</i> spp.	Sweep net	14.8	83.8
<i>Micrapis discolor</i>	Sweep net	11.6	78.4
<i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i>	Sweep net	4.8	40.5
RSV	Direct count	5.2(%) ^b	42.9

^aNumber/50 hills or 50 sweeps except eggs, which were taken from 10 hills. ^b% infected hills of 50 hills.

low, 4.8/50 sweeps at 41% of the sites. There were 61.4 BPH eggs/ 10 hills in dissected stems, but an average 61% of eggs were parasitized, mostly by *Anagrus* sp. and *Oligosita* sp.

Sixty-six percent of fields sampled

had transplanted rice. The remainder had direct, wet-seeded. RD1, RD7, and RD11 predominated. High rates of nitrogenous fertilizers, ranging from 24 to 89 kg N/ha (av 46 kg N/ha) were applied. Most farmers used a 16-20-0 fertil-

izer formulation. Two or three insecticide applications per growing season were made to 94% fields sampled. Carbofuran, monocrotophos, and carbaryl were the most common insecticides. Application rates were lower than recommended dosages — 10-20 g or ml/ 20 liters water for spray formulation, and 0.5 kg ai/ ha for granular formulation.

Results indicated outbreaks of BPH and RSV are probably caused by cultivation practices. Farmers grow susceptible high tillering varieties, apply high fertilizer rates, and practice double or continuous cropping. Insecticides may not be critical to insect outbreaks. Damage by BPH and RSV will increase because of high insect density and disease reservoirs unless farmers adopt new insect-resistant varieties and modern pest management practices. *h*

Predatory potential of the wolf spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata* on rice brown planthopper

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Several species of spiders in rice ecosystems prey on and effectively regulate rice leafhoppers and planthoppers. The wolf spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata* is the predominant species in irrigated wetland rice at Coimbatore, India. To determine the predatory potential of wolf spider on

brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*, glasshouse studies were made at Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore.

In the first experiment, 20 5th-instar BPH nymphs were placed on potted rice plants as food for each spider. In the second experiment, 20 adult BPH (10 brachypterous and 10 macropterous forms) were used. Fourth-instar spiders were used in both experiments and all the spiders molted at least once during the 15-day experimental period. Ten replications (hills) were maintained in

each experiment.

The number of BPH eaten or killed by each spider was recorded daily. A constant population of live BPH in the same stage was maintained. The same spiders were used throughout the experiment.

Each spider consumed an average of 6 5th-instar BPH nymphs/day. When brachypterous and macropterous adults at 1:1 were provided as food, each spider consumed 7 adults/day. Spiders did not prefer one form to the other. *h*

Life history of rice bug *Leptocoris oratorius* (F.)

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The life history of the rice bug *Leptocoris oratorius* (F.) was studied in the greenhouse at 27.4° C (range 20.5-34.3° C) and relative humidity of 81% (range 63.0-93.8%).

Newly laid eggs from an adult colony maintained on potted plants were clipped from leaves and placed on moist filter paper in a petri dish for incubation. Emerging nymphs were transferred in pairs to milk-stage panicles of potted

1. Mylar film cage measures 7.5 cm in diameter, 30 cm long. Nylon mesh sleeves at the ends are 13 cm long.

plants enclosed in mylar film cages (Fig. 1).

The bugs laid eggs in single or double rows on the leaves and sometimes singly on the panicles of the potted plants. Eggs hatched in 7.5 days (range of 6-9) and nymphs passed through 5 instars with an average nymphal period of 20.5 days (range 19-22). Preoviposition and egg laying periods were 18.0 days (range 9-25) and 57.0 days (range 6-108). Average life span was 80.0 days (26-134). Each female laid an average of 284.5 eggs (range 0-569) during 108 days of egg laying (Fig. 2). Gravid females laid eggs on leaves of potted plants at late booting rather than at milk stage. ^k

2. Fecundity and longevity of rice bugs. IRRI, 1982. a = preoviposition period, b = peak, b + c = egg-laying period, a to d = longevity.

***Propicrosscytus mirificus* (Girault) [Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae] correct name for the larval parasite of rice gall midge**

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Obtusiclava oryzae Subba Rao is the most important larval parasite of rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-

Mason) in India, Indonesia, and Thailand. It is also the type-species of the genus *Obtusiclava* Subba Rao, 1973 [ref: Subba Rao, B.R. 1973. Descriptions of a new species and genus of *Pteromalidae* (Hymenoptera) parasitic on *Pachydidiplosis oryzae* (Wood-Mason) (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae). Bull. Ent. Res. 62:627-29]. In 1978, after examining Girault's types in Queensland Museum, Australia, Boucek discovered that the *Obtusiclava* is the same genus as *Propicrosscytus Szelenyi*, 1941. Fur-

thermore, *Propicrosscytus mirificus* (Girault) has a new junior synonym in *O. oryzae* Subba Rao [ref: Boucek, Z. et al 1978. A preliminary review of *Pteromalidae* (Hymenoptera) of India and adjacent countries. Oriental Ins. 12(4):433-67]. Henceforth, the genus *Propicrosscytus* Szelenyi, 1941, having been described earlier, has priority over *Obtusiclava* Subba Rao, 1973. Therefore, the correct name for *O. oryzae* Subba Rao is *Propicrosscytus mirificus* (Girault). ^k

Soil and crop management

Increasing nitrogen use efficiency in transplanted rice by blending urea with margosa seed cake powder

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Margosa (*Azadirachta indica*) seeds contain an alkaloid called *nimbidin* that inhibits soil nitrification. Margosa cake is cheap and locally available at several places in India. Used in combination with urea, it can increase nitrogen use efficiency in rice. However, when powdered country-pressed deoiled margosa cake is mixed with urea (15-30% wt/ wt) the two do not adhere.

Effect of urea blended with margosa cake powder (MCP) on transplanted Jaya during 1980 kharif, Pantnagar, India

N rate (kg/ha)	N application method	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	Yield response (kg grain/kg N)
0	No nitrogen	3.2	-
50	Urea mixed with 15% MCP, basal incorporated	5.3	42
50	Urea mixed with 30% MCP, basal incorporated	4.6	28
50	Urea coated with 15% MCP with coal tar and kerosene oil, basal incorporated	5.3	42
50	Urea coated with 30% MCP with coal tar and kerosene oil, basal incorporated	5.0	36
50	Urea coated with coal tar and kerosene oil, basal incorporated	5.1	38
50	Urea basal incorporated	4.7	30
50	Urea band-placed at about 5 cm depth	4.8	32
50	Urea best split	5.1	38
100	Urea best split	6.6	34
	S.Em ±	0.24	
	C.D. at 5%	0.70	
	C.V. (%)	9.9	

^aAt 14% moisture.